

MHD Unsteady Free Convection of Heat and Mass Transfer Flow through Porous Medium with Time Dependent Suction and Constant Heat Source/Sink

Authors : Dr. Praveen Saraswat, Dr. Rudraman Singh

Abstract : In this paper we have investigated the free convection MHD flow due to heat and mass transfer through porous medium bounded by an infinite vertical non-conducting porous plate with time dependent suction under the influence of uniform transverse magnetic field of strength H_0 . When Temperature (T) and Concentration (C) at the plate is oscillatory with time about a constant non-zero mean. The velocity distribution, the temperature distribution, co-efficient of skin friction and role of heat transfer is investigated. Here the partial differential equations are involved. Exact solution is not possible so approximate solution is obtained and various graphs are plotted.

Keywords : Time Dependent Suction, Convection, MHD, Porous

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014